

Academic Performance - Study Field D2

Educational Systems and Capacity Building

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A Comparison of the Egyptian and German Educational Systems

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Abstract:

This study aims to compare the educational systems of Egypt and Germany and sheds light on their historical, cultural and economic profiles. In addition, the current study digs deeper into the Egyptian and German educational systems presenting their history and political eras that affected the formation and elaboration of their timeline via a thorough inspection of details. Furthermore, the current study attempts to reveal both of the similarities and differences in view of careful readings, comparing literature, and education experts' opinions. This paper demonstrates the importance of exchanging experiences and mutual learning from systems all over the world. Cross-border education is now inevitable and its multitude of opportunities and benefits cannot be ignored. Knowledge has to prevail in the entire world without any sort of science acquisition or limitation, or exclusively in a limited part of the world. The world is for everyone. If we do not acknowledge it, education will suffer and eventually economy and people shall suffer. Finally, the study aims to present and analyze the educational history of both nations, and it should not be understood as an encroachment on sovereignty, but rather as a global thinking and direction.

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2- Introduction

Education is a right... Same as water and air..... A famous aphorism of the well-known blind dean of Arabic literature and the late Egyptian Minister of Education in 1970, Dr.Taha Hussein. Education is a pillar of the construction of peoples and communities. Any educational system is designed based upon several pillars; where ideology, principles, beliefs, and values truly define the educational goals and provide general guidance along with other ecological factors. Ultimately, linking individuals to their surrounding environment .

Education is the magic wand used to enlighten and civilize people and guide them to the right path. When educational organizations set their policies and practices, they should not lose sight of interdependence between them on one hand, and the society and the rest of the world on the other hand. Education is as open as air; it is not associated to one single homeland. Yet, education itself is a homeland, as Bloom (1972) warned us long time ago that we need to “Put our house in order” (p. 334), and as noted by (Hu,G, 2009, p131) “The burden of responsibility for appropriate actions and practices rests with the professionals in the field” (p. 349) ⁽¹⁾. This paper presents different educational systems and stresses on the importance of exchanging experiences and learning from systems from around the world. According to Fegan (2009), cross-border education is inevitable and encompasses countless opportunities and benefits that cannot be ignored. However, it is not meant to imply that a free-for-all approach, where content’s quality and delivery and contextualized understanding are crucially imperative. Reforming structures and systems without simultaneous reform in thinking will merely repeat what has been introduced but in new skins.

Cross-border education should not be understood as an encroachment on sovereignty, but rather as global thinking and direction. Knowledge has to prevail in the entire world without any sort of science acquisition or limitation, or exclusively in a limited part of the world. The world is for everyone. If we do not acknowledge it, education will suffer and

eventually economy and people shall suffer. (p.17).⁽²⁾ Owen (2006) notes that “Educational politics, like politics in general, revolves around three entities: people, values, and resources”. Owen showed that education leaders with no political acumen and a sad lack of political administration are the main reason for the deterioration of education in schools. In addition, it shows the impact of politics and how it affects local education, and how administrators read the political climate of a community, analyze collected information, and proactively manage political issues in order to maintain a stable school environment.⁽³⁾

Indeed, policymaking is highly connected to education, and education is highly influenced by policy makers. Just as in developed countries where educational policies are reframed to fit the general direction of the country, while on the contrary, in developing countries, educational policies are linked to governmental and personal interests.

3. Education in Egypt

3.1 History of Egypt's Educational System

In fact, I prefer to start on this paper by discussing the educational system in Egypt, starting with Mohamed Ali –Ottoman’s era in the early nineteenth century. The Egyptians did not forget his efforts and thoughts .According to Louisa Love Luck (2012) who said that the progress of Egypt’s education system has been affected by political systems.

The European-style system was first put in by Ottoman rulers in the early nineteenth century in order to nurture a class of well-educated, loyal administrators and army officers who would become the national army. From 1882 to 1922, being under the British occupation, investment in education was curbed drastically, and secular public schools, which had been free up to this time, began to charge fees. It has been suggested that this down scaling was partly designed to refashion graduates as administrators in the colonial bureaucracy and even to reduce the risk that potentially disruptive, educated, nationalist leaders might emerge to challenge the occupation

The presidency of Gamal Abdel Nasser offered education became a central part of the modernizing project. In the 1950s, he phased in free education for all Egyptian citizens, starting with schools and later extending this to include higher education. The Egyptian curriculum became a model for the region, greatly influencing other Arab education systems, which often employed Egyptian-trained teachers. Nasser also offered guarantees that all university graduates would be able to find employment in the public sector, a promise that contributed to a rapid increase in university enrollment rates in the following decades. Demand soon outstripped the level of available state resources, causing the quality of publicly provided education to deteriorate; rapid growth necessitated the hiring of insufficiently qualified teachers and placed an immense strain on school facilities. Many schools started to operate in shifts, especially in densely populated urban areas. Today this trend in public-sector education has culminated in poor teacher-student ratios (often around one to fifty) and persistent gender inequality. Female enrollment ratios are typically around 20percent lower than those of males, drop-out ratios are higher, and although there have been substantial improvements in female literacy rates, There remains a sizable gender gap in educational attainment. There also exists a parallel private education sector that dates back to President Anwar Sadat's 'Open Door' policies of the 1970s. The quality of education provided by many of these schools is vastly superior to that on offering the state system, and its beneficiaries often find themselves better equipped than their state-school counterparts for the labor market (p.4).⁽⁴⁾

I would agree with this saying "The education system now reflected the mixed economy and divided culture (...) attending a foreign school and speaking a foreign language became the ticket to increased income." (Cochran 1986).⁽⁵⁾

Since Mubarak started to rule, he encouraged the idea of private education as he encouraged that in the economic sector (Farag, 2006, p.22).⁽⁶⁾

By the emergence of various educational systems such as American, British, German and French education, etc., the negligence started within government education. Sobhy pointed out that adult literacy (15+) has been officially estimated at around 70.4% in 2007 (UNDP 2010), but actual literacy skills are not independently measured across the system for actual students. Internationally comparable figures from Trends in International Mathematics and Science Study (TIMSS) examinations place education quality in Egypt below the international average, but higher than most sub-Saharan African countries.

(MOE 2006) .In addition, of those who enrolled in secondary education in 2005/06, 32.9% went to general secondary, 56.3% studied in technical schools, 8% studied in Azhar religious schools and 2.7% studied in private general secondary schools (MOE 2006, Annex 2, 77). Moreover, the teacher's salaries are so low and this issue is frequently discussed in the press where, for example, it is reported that 8254 out of 13,000 teachers in one rural province were hired on the 120 EGP per month temporary contracts (Al-Badil. 2011).

In addition, a study of a number of urban and rural technical and general schools in Giza, Egypt, found that more than 60% of students said that their in-school tutor is their regular school teacher and more than 30% said that their private lesson teacher is also their regular teacher (Megahed 2004, 144–7). In a study of a high-performing public preparatory school, Linda Herrera (1992) found that only a minority of teachers used tactics of intimidation, poor teaching, favoritism, and sometimes physical punishment so that students in their class would take private lessons with them. While realities in the technical schools may be similar to many ‘industrial’ technical schools across the country, there is no doubt that conditions could be better in other schools, such as commercial schools and girls’ schools, due to lower teacher shortages, fewer resource problems with workshop machinery and materials, and less pressure on students to work while studying.(sobhy,2012).⁽⁷⁾

In Ola Mohamed's thesis (2017), she explains the era in a realistic way explaining that the educational system was included with caring and improving the quality by Mubarak and MOE. they launched the initiative "Education for All " which confirmed the importance of improving quality. During the 1990s, a shift from a quantitative to qualitative emphasis occurred with the rise of the discourse of the World Conference on (Ginsburg & Megahed, 2008). Nonetheless, despite various efforts, the education system today continues to suffer from deficiencies in quality that may be very well attributed to the hierarchical and centralized policies implemented by the state (George Eckert Institute, 2009; Nasser-Ghodsi, 2006). I would totally agree with Ola Mohamed (2017) in opinion about returning the deterioration of education and its quality to the centralization and dominance of the Ministry of Education and Egyptian law and the lack of innovative ideas and ideas for the compatibility of education to serve different sectors of the Egyptian. (p.26).⁽⁸⁾

After the revolution of 2011, the revolution came with rosy dreams demanding that Egyptians live freely without police oppression and fruition social justice. What happened after the revolution is only the contradictory of the requirements of the Egyptians .in addition to the economic deterioration, high unemployment rates, security, moral insecurity, and as a result of this impunity, education has deteriorated and many students have not been able to go to schools for a number of years.

4. Education in Germany

4.1 History of German Educational System

"I cannot and will not recant anything, for to go against conscience is neither right nor safe. Here I stand; I can do no other, so help me God. Amen "Martin Luther"

I started before, the description of the beginning of the education system in Egypt at the hands of Muhammad Ali, his educational progress, and his interest in Kuttab and religion basics in Egypt where people had to learn the Quran as a start as well. When moving to

Germany in the 16th Century we find the same religious direction, Martin Luther has made a significant development to the history of religious education. He called for equality in education between boys and girls, besides establishment of a number of schools to contribute to the preaching of children and teaching the Christian religion, Luther explains that education is a divine matter that stems from the Bible. This kind of religious education had spread all over Germany until the 18th Century. (McKinney, Professor Stephen, 2017).⁽⁹⁾

Here the features of compulsory education began to appear in the Prussian era despite racial discrimination between social levels and gender (1740-86) when Frederick the Great of Prussia mandated regular school attendance from the ages of 5 through 13 or 14. The denominational or confessional school remained the norm throughout Prussia (which encompassed the Rhineland and most of modern Germany) during the nineteenth century. In Prussia, efforts to establish schools in which Catholic, Protestant, and Jewish children could receive a common education, separated only in religion classes, failed, despite several serious efforts at reform. In the cities, free, public schools educated children of the working class, while public schools, which had some fees, attracted children of middle-class families and offered a stricter curriculum. Women, in low numbers, participated in the teaching profession in the late 1800s.

From the beginning of the nineteenth century, the concept of the education system had changed in Prussia after Friedrich William III's defeat against Napoleon. So it forced Frederick to improve education and eliminate differences between classes and rely on skills, not the social background. All children entered the education system without setting strict breaks. The responsibilities of the Gymnasium (a secondary school preparing boys for university admission) were expanded to include the preparation of civil servants, a task later assumed by the intermediate secondary schools. By 1900 the Gymnasium had developed three basic

models providing for a specialization in the classical languages, modern languages, or mathematics and science. Girls were not accepted to the Gymnasium until 1908 and not admitted to Prussian universities until 1910. (www.Germany-HISTORY-BACKGROUND, 3&4 paragraphs).⁽¹⁰⁾

During the First World War Germany suffered greatly and was presented with many problems politically, economically, and socially. Following the collapse of the Kaiser and loss of the First World War In 1919-1933, Germany was transformed in less than a year from a militaristic and autocratic monarchy into a democratic republic by the Weimar Republic.

The concept of educational autonomy gained wider acceptance. By this is meant the view that the methods and aims of education should be defined solely by reference to those who are involved in the educational process. In other words, education should not be the servant of political, social, or economic ends, but should rather concern itself primarily with the requirements of each pupil, so that the maximum personal development might be attained. To define educational policy one should not look beyond the welfare of the individual child (Martin G W, 1972, p.32).⁽¹¹⁾

According to Martin (1972), After the Nazi years, the teachers which were believed with Nazism, they were not easy getting rid or replaced after the war, and Germany passed through very difficult periods as a result of this thought, which hindered cultural development. Schools collapsed after the Nazi bombing and wars, so schools should be rebuilt. West Germany was slower in its educational innovation in order not to show the difference built between it and GDR and appear too left-wing. (p.150).

In 1976 the Soviets established their vision administrative area to make the school system in Germany more "democratic ".they believe that they have to remove the tripartite Weimar system and replace it with a step-by-step organized "democratic" unitary school. In 1974The Western Allies also became politically active in their zones and required

restructuring the German education system by an educational commission of experts set up by the United States President Harry S. Truman. According to the so-called Zook Commission. Finally, the U.S. military government realized that the enforcement of its re-education policies in an authoritarian manner didn't work and didn't make any progress. For that reason they changed their strategic priorities and no longer insisted on those set out in Control Council Directive 54 structural reform.

Thus, in 1955, with the Düsseldorf Agreement, the tripartite school structure was established as the cross-federal standard of school organization. At the beginning of 1960s, it became clear that the rigid adherence to the tripartite system caused various problems.

A comparative study initiated by the OECD showed clear modernization deficits in both the areas of elementary school and high school education. The philosopher and educator Georg Picht warned in 1964 in a well-regarded book of the impending "German educational catastrophe", in the reconstruction phase, and the sociologist Hansger Peisert also drew the attention to the massive under representation of various population groups in higher education institutions. Education in Germany is still not realized as a "civil right". The sociologist and later FDP politician Ralf Dahrendorf in his influential "Plea for an active educational policy" (1965) warned: Legal equality remains fiction.

There was a change in the educational system in 1969 When the SPD-led coalition took over the government for the first time in German history. An amendment to the Basic Law gave the federal government the opportunity to work together with the federal states in planning education, the "Federal Ministry of Education and Science". The following year the "Federal-State Commission for Educational Planning" (BLK) set up and entrusted with the task of drafting a long-term plan for the further development of the entire education system.

The aim was, among other things, to expand and open middle and higher education and to focus more on science in the elementary school level, which - extended by a ninth year and

separated from the primary school - now became an independent school type, the secondary school. Teaching and school life should also change fundamentally, and more attention has been paid to technical and social learning. In order to strengthen the learners' opportunities to participate in school, forms of democratic participation (such as student representation including the need for increased rights for women and gender equality) were anchored. The learners also focused on methodology and didactics. The lessons became more student- and action-oriented, Teaching and learning forms characterized by reform pedagogy became more important. (www.bpd.de).⁽¹²⁾

we turn to the period of reforms in the seventies and eighties.

In 1970, the Bund-Länder-Kommission (BLK) für Bildungsplan Und was established and founded in 1970 as a commission for educational planning by an administrative agreement between the federal government and the Länder. After receiving additional tasks in 1975, the name was changed to “Bund-Länder-Kommission für Bildungsplanung und Forschungsförderung” (BLK), with effect from April 5, 1976. Thus, BLK worked closely with the Ministry of Foreign Affairs to enhance progress in education and provide funds for innovation and development of projects to create innovative theory and practice in German education. Moreover, Kindergarten was merged with elementary education and became one part. As for secondary education In 1973 the FRG decided to set up comprehensive schools. The Bund-Länder Kommission für Bildungsplanung (German Federal Development Commission) presented a comprehensive training plan for western Germany. The main aim was to design a uniform of preschool education, general school, vocational training, and continuous education and training.

1990 was called the reunion that had a direct impact on the educational system in Germany. The new situation led to the evolvement of the school system in the former GDR. The new states in the east of Germany were guided by the Hamburg Agreement in the design of their

school systems. A Joint Education Commission called “GemeinsameBildungskommission” of both former German countries was established. This commission agreed about the future of the educational system. The negotiating partners had difficult discussions about different possibilities for the future design of German education and were influenced by the Current situation on the markets as well as on future challenges in the pedagogy and technology fields. The concept was presented in the handout for the development of syllabi framework of the KMK for vocational education and training in vocational schools for apprenticeship and their coordination with federal Training regulations for recognized professions. The introduced approach is called learning field concept for vocational schools (Lernfeld-Konzept). This approach is now mandatory for apprenticeships and changes the whole learning in VET. With the learning field concept, the traditional division of subjects was abolished in most of the vocational school forms. The learning fields are part of the syllabus and are based on real situations in enterprises with operational actions. A learning field can summarize several fields of action. Another core idea of the KMK was a new aim for vocational schools. The goal is to promote the competence of the learners and to foster their willingness for lifelong learning in teaching at vocational schools. Therefore, the KMK focused on the topics of professional competence/subject-related competence, human/self-competence, and social competence. In Germany the internet, new media, and IT became increasingly important, further influencing education.

After the millennium, the PISA- Shock- hit German education although all these reforms. Society and politicians were shocked by the average results of Germany at the first PISA study which was regarded as weak. A discussion on equal opportunities for learners started and led to redesigns of the educational system in additionally, the ideas of Bologna were taken into account to these changes.(Beutner, M., &Pechuel, R. ,2017).⁽¹³⁾

In summary, we must admit that it is not easy to reach a stable and successful educational policy 100%. But the repeated attempts made by Germany to improve its educational policy are a success in itself. Germany was not stopped to reformulate an appropriate education and participate in decision-making, despite the political, economic and social changes as well. Insistence in measuring changes in various aspects and elaborating them in educational policies and appropriate laws is the essence of success.

5. Educational Systems

5.1 Egyptian Educational system:

Structure of the education system (2007)

Figure 1-Source: MOE, 2007

In the beginning, we will describe the structure of the educational system in Egypt that is established from MOE to the Types of public schools. Two main types of government schools: Arabic schools and official language schools. Other Types of private schools. There are four types of private schools: Ordinary schools have quite a similar curriculum to that of the public Arabic schools but more resources to the school facilities and infrastructure.

Language schools that teach most of the official curriculum in English, and add French or German as a second foreign language.

Religious schools include the al-Azhar schools (administered by the Islamic al-Azhar University and open only to Muslim students), Catholic schools and schools of other denominations, International schools are private schools that follow another country's curriculum (e.g. the American, British, French or German systems). These schools offer the American high school diploma, the British International General Certificate of Secondary Education (IGCSE), the French baccalauréat, the German Abitur or the International Baccalaureate. Their qualifications must receive official government certification from the Ministry of Education in order for the students to be eligible to enroll in Egyptian universities. Also, students have to study and succeed in Arabic and religion and social studies. (Ministry of Education, 2010, p38)⁽¹⁵⁾

5.1.1 Kindergarten Education

Pre-school education (kindergarten): the structure figure did not mention this period but it's actually part of all schools in Egypt. It is an independent educational stage lasting for two years for children aged 4-5 years, providing access to early childhood programs and considered as a priority. Early childhood schools charge relatively high fees. (Egypt; World data on education, 2010/11; 2012)⁽¹⁴⁾. In spite of that, there is much organization of providers offering some level of service at this stage of education. such as the Ministry of Education, the Ministry of Social Solidarity, the National Council for Childhood and Motherhood (NCCM), the al-Azhar system, a number of international and local non-governmental organizations (NGOs) and some co-operatives and the private sector. (OECD, 2015, p35).⁽¹⁴⁾

5.1.2 Primary, Preparatory Education:

Compulsory basic education starts at age 6 and covers primary and preparatory.

These basic years of education are a right for Egyptian. Between 1988 and 1999, primary education lasted five years, divided into two levels, of three and two years' duration respectively. In accordance with the Law No. 23 of 1999, compulsory basic education now lasts nine years and covers the six-year primary education cycle and the three-year preparatory cycle. At the end of primary education, pupils who successfully pass the exam receive the completion certificate. At the end of the three-year preparatory cycle, students sit a centrally-set examination and if they pass them successfully, they are awarded the basic education completion certificate. Pupils who are not able to complete the preparatory cycle can opt for a vocational program offered in vocational schools; trainees who successfully complete the program receive the certificate of completion of basic education and vocational preparation (ibe,2010).

5.1.3 Secondary Education:

Secondary education is divided into two branches, namely General Secondary Education and Technical Secondary Education. The volume of students enrolled in secondary education is more than technical secondary highlighting the rise in demand for general secondary education. That requires students getting a high score on prep school from 70-75%. The General and technical secondary education for three years. Technical education (mainly in the areas of industry, agriculture and commerce) is offered at two levels: three-year programs preparing middle-level technicians, and five-year programs preparing high-level technicians. Students who pass the exams at the end of general secondary education are awarded the General Secondary Education Certificate. Students who pass the exams at the end of three-year technical programs receive the Secondary School Technical Diploma (in

commerce, industry, agriculture); those who pass the centrally-set examinations at the end of the five-year program are awarded the Diploma of Advanced Technical Studies.

Al-Azhar (religious) education schools place more emphasis on Islamic studies. Upon completion of the program, students are awarded the Al-Azhar Secondary School Certificate. Intermediate technical institutes offer two-year, post-secondary programs leading to the award of diplomas in several areas (social services, health sciences, industry, and commerce), giving access to a higher institute or a university program in a similar allotment. (Ibrahim, 2010).

The Ministry of Education pointed out that the new system (the new Cumulative Secondary School System will be implemented at Japanese and public Arabic schools). will be applied for the first time in the academic year 2018/2019; accordingly, students will sit a total of 12 examinations through their three years in high school—each year they will sit four examinations. The Ministry also noted that the cumulative result will be calculated based on the mean of the four examinations in which students scored highest. Furthermore, the Ministry indicated that the 750,000 educational tablets, which are meant to help students study in a more innovative and original way. (Reda, 2018).⁽¹⁶⁾

5.1.4 Higher Education

Figure 2-Structure of public higher education in Egypt. Source Strategic Planning Unit(SPU)/Ministry of Higher Education (MHE)(2013)

After secondary school or technical high school, students look to the university stage according to the total score of each student. As shown in the figure, there are governmental universities, technical universities, and private universities, and to Al-Azhar University which is the oldest university in Egypt and the Arab world.

Furthermore it Higher institutes offer four-year professional programs leading to the award of a diploma equivalent to a bachelor's degree; an additional two years lead to the award of a master's degree. A few higher institutes of technology also offer three- year programs leading to a higher diploma of technology. Universities offer both academic and professional programs. The duration of programs leading to a bachelor's degree or a 'licence' is generally four years (five years in the case of dentistry, pharmacy, veterinary medicine, engineering and fine arts; six years in the case of medicine.)(See also: NUFFIC, 2010).⁽¹⁷⁾

5.2 German Educational system

Figure 3-<https://www.nuffic.nl/en/publications/find-a-publication/education-system-germany.pdf>.

Actually, wisdom and logic in educational policies direct us to the decentralization of the educational system, and here in Germany who presents a success lesson "decentralized system" to serve the states and provide their needs and requirements. The education system is divided into, early childhood education. schools Kindertagesstätte - sponsored by child-care service institutions that are not part of the school system, then primary education is a compulsory education a rule general compulsory schooling begins for all children in the Federal Republic of Germany in the year in which they reach the age of six and involves nine years of full-time schooling (ten years in Berlin, Brandenburg, Bremen, and Thüringen; in Nordrhein-Westfalen, the duration of full-time compulsory education is nine years for the

Gymnasium, and ten years for other general education schools), secondary education, post-secondary education, and continuing education. (KMK,2015/2016)⁽¹⁸⁾.

5.2.1 Primary Education:

As we indicated in the previous paragraph, primary education is the first stage of compulsory education in the Federal Republic of Germany so-called Grundschule. It covers grades 1 to 4. In Berlin and Brandenburg the Grundschule covers grades 1 to 6.

Source: on [move.ph-ludwigsburg.de/2018/D2 Educational Systems and Capacity](http://move.ph-ludwigsburg.de/2018/D2_Educational_Systems_and_Capacity_Building/Attendance_Phase/Pictures_of_the_two_days/22.jpg)

Building/Attendance Phase/Pictures of the two days/22.jpg.

According to the Standing Conference of the Ministers of Education and Cultural Affairs, (Kultusministerkonferenz – KMK) resolved recommendations on the work in the primary school. According to the recommendations, the task of the primary school is to enable basic school education in a joint educational program for all children.

The goal is to acquire and extend basic and adaptable competences. These include above all the key competences of reading and writing as well as mathematics, which form a basis

For not only all other educational areas in the primary school but also for continuing Education as well as lifelong learning and independent appropriation of culture.

There are three types of schools (Hauptschule, Realschule, and Gymnasium) categorizing and directing students according to their academic abilities, the desires of their families, and the decision of the recommendation from the primary school teachers.

5.2.2 Secondary Education

It is worth noting, that secondary education is divided into two sections:

1-lower secondary level (Sekundarstufe I), it is Hauptschulen ,Realschulen

,Gymnasien,andGesamtschuleits a cooperative secondary school which bring together the Hauptschule, Realschule, and Gymnasium under one pedagogical and organizational roof.

All these schools are considered a preparatory stage for the upper secondary stage offering one single course of education. The Hauptschule provides its pupils a basic central educational. According to their performance and preferences, through specialization, and Subject to their qualifications, to continue their education with basic education, which then qualifies him for individual specialization vocational that depend on the abilities and knowledge skills.

***-Hauptschule** covers grades 5–9. With ten years of compulsory full-time education, the Hauptschule also includes grade 10. Moreover, the courses aren't only

Leading to join a vocational qualification, but also leading to a higher education entrance qualification to join a Fachoberschule, a more practical kind of high-school, working toward a possible enrollment in a Fachhochschule. In general, Haupt School leads to part-time enrollment in a vocational school combined with apprenticeship training “Berufsschule” until the age of 18.

***Realschulen** covers grades 5-10. The Realschule provides its pupils' more extensive learning according to their performance and preferences. As shown in the previous picture,

Realschule makes it easy for pupils to join Fachoberschule directly or higher education entrance qualification depending on the academic achievement of the student.

***Gymnasien** covers provide grades from 5-12 & 5- 13 (or years 7 to 12 following a six-primary school).As a previous photo shows, the Gymnasium schools include both two sections lower and upper secondary level . Apart from standard Gymnasien, there are special types of Gymnasium into which Hauptschule and Realschule pupils can transfer following grade 6 or 7, as well as special courses for particularly able Realschule and vocational school leavers. The Gymnasium leads to a diploma called the Abitur and prepare students for university study or for a dual academic and vocational credential; moreover, the gymnasium is supported by a strong lobby in western Germany and conservative politicians, particularly in the southern regions of Germany, and claims that it is the best school form in the world. Indeed, it is by far the number one in the PISA league table. However, some hold the opinion that "this success comes at the cost of a catastrophe in the Hauptschulen".

(www.howtogermany,German School System paragraph,5).⁽²⁰⁾

*** The Gesamtschule** it's a comprehensive school that is only found in some of the states. It takes the place of both the Hauptschule and Realschule. It enrolls students of all ability levels in the 5th through the 10th grades. Students who satisfactorily complete the Gesamtschule through the 9th grade receive the Hauptschule certificate, while those who satisfactorily complete schooling through the 10th grade receive the Realschule certificate.

2-Secondary school 2(Sekunadrestuffe 2)

We move here to the supplementary stage of the secondary system, depending on the amount of student excellence and on his professional and cognitive tendency.

Full-time vocational schools include the Berufsfachschule, the Fachoberschule, and the Berufliches Gymnasium.

***Berufsschule**

After the Hauptschule and Realschule lies the Berufsschule, combining part-time academic study and apprenticeship. The successful completion of an apprenticeship program leads to certification in a particular trade or field of work. These schools differ from the other ones mentioned in that control. They exist not by the local and regional school authorities, but by the federal government, industry and the trade unions.

*** Fachoberschule**

Fachoberschule: covers grades 11 and 12 and requires a Mittlerer Schulabschluss. Then it heads up to Fachhochschulreife, i.e. higher education entrance qualification. The Länder may also establish a grade 13. After successful completion of grade 13, pupils can obtain the Fachgebundene Hochschulreife.

*** Berufliches Gymnasium** Providing a 3-year long secondary education program, leading to an Abitur.

***Berufsoberschule**. Covers a two-year general and in-depth education and training, leading up to a vocational qualification (or Abitur – by proving the good command in second foreign language). There is also a 3/4 year course of study which is aimed at getting a double qualification, both vocational and higher education qualification.

***Berufsfachschule**”. Offers education for one or few professions which require formal recognition or leads to a vocational training qualification. (www.studying-in-germany.org)⁽²⁰⁾

Furthermore, there are different schools for students with special needs called Sonderschule or Förderschule. These schools are staffed with specially trained teachers. But some students prefer to attend regular schools and are integrated into a Hauptschule or Gesamtschule.

As for private education, there are a number of private schools in Germany that charge tuition fees, and offer varied courses leading to Abitur as well as other diplomas.

The shock is that Germany talked about after PISA 2000 about educational performance decline. Immediately the KMK put forth a seven-point plan of action to improve Germany's results. The points involved improving language skills in kindergarten, improving students' reading skills and understanding of math and science, supporting children and youth of immigrant backgrounds and/or from families unaccustomed to study, further developing and quality-assuring education in regard to standards and evaluations, improving teacher professionalism and making it possible to offer all-day school programs like the afterschool programs that are common in, for instance, Sweden (KMK Niederschriften, 2001–2012: NS296; cf. KMK Niederschriften, 2001–2012: NS298). (Ringarp, 2016).⁽²²⁾

5.2.3 Higher education

Higher education is the last stage of formal education and optional. The quality at all higher education institutions is equally good. As following, types of higher education is offered in the following forms:

Universities: universities impart theoretical knowledge. The course is very academically oriented like (Technische Universität, TU) or colleges of education (Pädagogische Hochschule, PH). At a university, you can also study for a doctorate (doctoral degree).

Universities of Applied Sciences (Fachhochschulen and Hochschulen für angewandte Wissenschaften) offers practice-oriented academic courses. The focus is on professional application more than theory.

Colleges of art, film, and music: Theologische Hochschulen; Kunsthochschulen and Musikhochschulen

Dual universities :(learning by doing) it's an additional program alongside a classic University of Applied Sciences. This course gives a chance to link the academic training with the professional life.

6. Primary Education in Egypt and in German

Faces of differences and similarities.	Egypt (Ebtadaey)	Germany (Grundschule)
Education Type	Compulsory	Compulsory
Duration of study	6 Years	4 Years But in Berlin and Brandenburg, the Grundschule covers grade 1-six
Age of admission	6 years in October <u>as</u> <u>must</u>	6 Years, at the end of vacation depending on which federal state the children settle in. <u>Early entrance</u> for children who have their sixth birthday after the statutory qualifying date as determined by the Länder may be permitted to start school early on their

		<p>parents' application.</p> <p>Compulsory schooling for such children starts with their admittance.(www.kmk,primary education,p.107)</p>
Teacher	<p>-All teachers are hired by the MOE.</p> <p>-For grades 1-3 all teachers teach all subjects</p> <p>-for grades 4-6 specialized teachers for each subject.</p>	<p>-All teachers are hired by the federal state authority.</p> <p>-from 1-4 all teachers teach all subjects.</p>
Curriculum	<p>the subjects taught are the same for all</p>	<p>the subjects taught are the same for all</p>
Evaluation	<p>-Grades 1, and 2 - a preparing process only based on formative assessments there is no student's fail. All children are passing to the third year by order of law. There is no recommendation from the teacher about if the student has not acquired the skills of reading, writing, and mathematics.</p>	<p>There are no terms exams just receive a recommendation from the teachers concerning the type of schools most suitable for their children through their reports of student's performance. to continue in the secondary stage.</p> <p>This recommendation is based on the teacher's evaluation of the child's performance,</p>

	-For grades 3, 4, 5, and 6, there are mid-year and year-end exams, in addition to the formative assessment scores that are set by the teacher during the school year.	abilities, and skills. If a child has learning difficulties, the teacher might recommend sending it to a special school for slow learners ((Sonderschule).
After primary education	-After the primary stage, children are move to prep school directly if the students passed grade six in mid-year and end year exams without any recommendations from teachers	After primary school students attend a Hauptschule, Mittelschule, RegionaleSchule or a Realschule, which are more vocationally direction, a Gymnasium, more academically direction, or a Gesamtschule, which is comparable to a Comprehensive School

In light of this comparison and experience that I spent in the Egyptian education system, Several points have come to my mind to benefit from the German system.

The Competence-oriented learning which depends on forms of performance assessment.

.1-Competence-oriented feedback of the process provides information on how far the individual child has progressed along the path to the target competences at the end of a learning pathway. It is the basis of the assessment.

These forms of Feedback instruments include competence-based reports, observation sheets, learning development reports, learning diaries and portfolios. In addition, pupils and their parents are familiar with these assessments to involve in the education range. This feedback takes place according to transparent criteria and illustrates the individual progress and standard competency level that has been achieved. For long time ago, this policy had been carried out in Egyptian education, but it did not last long and immediately changed with the change of minister, and this is what I will address in the next point.

2-In Germany, there is no overall federal authority. Even though there is a common basic structure in the educational system, the individual Länder are responsible for schooling and teacher education. It is a vivid example of decentralization. I hope that system will be transferred to Egypt but not as slogans hanged on the walls of Egyptian schools.

3-Improve the teacher's income and social conditions, such as insurance, Pensions and a good reputation within the community.

The German educational system can learn from the Egyptian education system by giving enough time for the student to determine which type of school he wants to apply in after the ninth grade. The student, the teacher and the parent will be sure of their decision. According to my own point of view, judging the student after grade four is considered a kind of cruelty and injustice.

7- Conclusion

This paper deals with a number of facts from various sources regarding two entirely different educational systems. In conclusion, based on these readings, it is absurd to try to entirely transplant an educational system of one state copying its whole structure to a different one, mainly due to considerable disparities in social, cultural and historical aspects. It shall always be taken into consideration that people are absolutely diversified in their cultural, social and economic dimensions, let alone the heterogeneous religious beliefs and vastly differed environmental and geographic features. Accordingly, the way we overlook and address all such differences ought to provide a unified educational system.

The readings shed the light upon an important point; educational systems should call for an *Education-For-All* approach. Therefore, we have to expand the circles of educational responsibilities in order to reduce centralization and dominance of one sector over the rest of people. An educational policy can unify us with all of our differences, and, by contrast, can separate us even if we are similar. In due regard, transferring ideas and skills across continents, as presented, highlights the fact that education is not limited to one province in the world, but rather to be considered as the essence of freedom.

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9- Appendix

Figure one-World Data on Education. 7th edition, 2010/11 http://www.ibe.unesco.org/fileadmin/user_upload/Publications/WDE/2010/pdf-versions/Egypt.pdf

(Figure 2:Radwan, M. M. (2016). Arab republic of Egypt. In Higher Education in the Middle East and North Africa (pp. 11-39). Springer, Singapore

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Figure 3-<https://www.nuffic.nl/en/publications/find-a-publication/education-system-germany.pdf>

Figure 4- On move.ph-ludwigsburg.de/2018/D2 Educational Systems and Capacity Building/Attendance Phase/Pictures of the two days/22jpg figure <https://move.ph-ludwigsburg.de/mod/lightboxgallery/view.php?id=12965#>

